

Evaluation of the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention administered in a mass campaign by health services in southern Senegal

Case report form for the control

1. Identification: *Includes all children under 10 years of age with no clinical signs of malaria and a negative RDT*

- District : _____ Health post : _____
- Village/Neighbourhood: _____ Name of village/neighbourhood head: _____
- Name head of concession: _____ Name head of household:

- Control name _____ ID : _____. Age |__|__| years |__|__| month
Sexe|__| M /F
- Mother's name

- Lives in the village since birth: |__| yes/No/don't know. If no, How many years has he lived in the village? |__|__| years
- Parent's phone number **: _____
- Name of the parent whose telephone number you have and relationship: _____

2. Mosquito nets. *Ask for the bed where the control usually sleeps and inspect the net*

- Does the child usually sleep under a bed net? |__| yes/No/don't know
- If yes, for how long: Less than 3 months |__| 3 to 6 months |__| More than 6 months |__|
- Did the child sleep under a net last night? |__| yes/No/don't know
- *Ask to see where the child usually sleeps and inspect the net*
- *About the mosquito net*
 - Where does it come from? Purchased |__| State |__| NGO |__| If yes which one _____
 - Has this net been treated at least once in the last 12 months? |__| yes/No/don't know
 - If no, is it a treated net |__| yes/No/don't know
 - if yes, what is the name of the LLIN? |__| olyset Net(1) Parmanet (2) Dawapulus (3) Iconelife (4) autres (5)
 - Can it be tucked under the mattress? |__| yes/No. Is it intact (<5 holes)? |__| yes/No

3. Insecticide spraying

- Does the control use an insecticide spray at home? |__| yes/No/don't know
- Has the control been house sprayed in the last 6 months? |__| yes/No/don't know

4. Last SMC dose given*** *Contact the child's mother or guardian. Inspect the child's CPS card*

- CPS card seen? |__| Yes/No

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